

Serum Afamin in Prediabetic Individuals in Association with Insulin Resistance and Glycemic Indices: A Case-Control Study

Barhav Abdullah

Corresponding author, Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, College of Health Sciences, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

Azzam Mosa

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

Sherwan Salih

Clinical Chemistry Department, College of Medicine, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

Jihan Jasim

Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, College of Health Sciences, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

Rondik Yousif

Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, College of Health Sciences, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

Shirav Mahmood

Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, College of Health Sciences, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

Dlin Yousif

Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, College of Health Sciences, University of Duhok, Duhok, Iraq

More Information

How to cite this article: Abdullah B, Mosa A, Salih S, Jasim J, Yousif R, Mahmood S, Yousif D. Serum Afamin in Prediabetic Individuals in Association with Insulin Resistance and Glycemic Indices: A Case-Control Study. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(4):86-91.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(4).11

Keywords:

afamin,
insulin resistance,
obesity,
serum glucose,
prediabetes.

Abstract

Background: Prediabetes is a metabolic disorder characterized by higher serum glucose levels than normal and below the diagnostic threshold for diabetes mellitus. Afamin is a glycoprotein mainly excreted from the liver and facilitates vitamin E transport. Afamin is one of the albumin gene family that includes albumin, α -Fetoprotein, and vitamin D-binding protein. **Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate serum afamin levels in prediabetic individuals and ascertain the association of serum afamin with insulin resistance and glycemic indices. **Material and Methods:** A case-control study was performed at Azadi Teaching Hospital, Kurdistan Region, Iraq, consisted of 88 participants, 44 prediabetic individuals and 44 apparently healthy individuals as a control group. Prediabetic individuals were obtained from relatives of patients with diabetes mellitus visiting Azadi Teaching Hospital, whereas, healthy individuals were chosen from the medical staff and college employees. The diagnosis of prediabetes was made according to the American Diabetes Association criteria. Serum afamin were assessed by Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay, while other biochemical parameters such as HbA1c, glucose and insulin were analyzed by Cobas 6000 (Roche, Hitachi/ Germany). **Results:** Mean level of serum afamin was higher in prediabetic individuals (115.31 ± 62.74) compared to their level in the control group (91.57 ± 43.46), with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.042$). The mean age of prediabetics was (44.05 ± 10.56) with males predominant (63.6%) and 70.5% of them were more than 40 years and 88.6% were obese. **Conclusion:** The study concluded the presence of higher mean serum afamin levels among prediabetic individuals compared to the healthy control.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Prediabetes is defined as a hyperglycemic state between normal glucose metabolism and diabetes mellitus [1]. According to American Diabetes Association (ADA), prediabetes classified into two categories depending on fasting and 2 hours post-load glucose concentration that includes impaired glucose tolerance (IGT), which is defined as post-load plasma glucose of 140–199 mg/dl (7.8–11.0 mmol/L) based on a 2-hour oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) with hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) percent of 5.7–6.4%, and impaired fasting glucose (IFG), which is defined as fasting plasma glucose (FPG) of 100–125 mg/dl (6.1–6.9 mmol/L) [2]. The majority of prediabetes individuals are mostly asymptomatic and can be considered as a strong predictor for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) development and cardiovascular disease (CVD) development [3].

Afamin is a glycoprotein found in human plasma with a molecular mass of 87 kDa, 15% carbohydrate content and 55% amino acid sequence similar to albumin [4]. It is primarily expressed in the liver but other tissues like the brain, testis, ovaries and kidneys can be responsible for its expression [5]. Overexpressing of the human afamin gene developed an increased body weight and increased blood concentrations of lipids and glucose [6]. It has been shown that afamin might have binding properties for two of the major forms of antioxidative vitamin E, α -tocopherol and γ -tocopherol, that might be of functional relevance for some diseases such as T2DM, metabolic syndrome, obesity, pregnancy complications, polycystic ovary syndrome, hypertension, dyslipidemia and as a tumor marker for ovarian cancer [7]. Several studies have made a connection between inflammatory markers and afamin, as it may be involved in several mechanisms, that could affect insulin sensitivity, resulting in insulin resistance that is intimately associated with inflammation [8].

The study was aimed to evaluate the serum afamin levels in prediabetic individuals and estimate the association of serum afamin levels with insulin resistance and glycemic indices in prediabetic individuals.

Materials and Methods

The current case-control study was conducted for 7 months from 1st of July 2023 to 30th January 2024. The study involves 88 participants, including 44 prediabetic individuals (selected from relatives of diabetic patients who visited the Diabetic and Endocrinology Unit of Azadi Teaching Hospital) and 44 apparently healthy individuals as a control group (selected from medical staff and college employees, with normal levels of FPG and HbA1c%). Individuals with liver diseases, kidney diseases, thyroid diseases, and any other existing

systemic diseases or taking drugs that would alert the biochemical parameters to be investigated were excluded, as well as pregnant women.

The study was approved by the College of Health Sciences/ Duhok University and the Research Ethics Committee of the General Directorate of Health at Duhok City and registered by reference number (13122023-11-24).

The participants filled out a questionnaire form in the meeting, providing information such as name, age, gender, and physical activity. Anthropometric parameters included the measurement of Waist Circumferences (WC), Weight and Height which were used for the calculation of Body Mass Index (BMI) which was determined as the weight in kilogram divided by height in meters square (kg/m^2) [9]. Prediabetes individuals were diagnosed according to the ADA criteria: either fasting serum glucose levels between 100 mg/dl and 125 mg/dl named IFG and serum glucose levels between 140 mg/dl and 199 mg/dl, 2 hours after OGTT with HbA1c between 5.8% to 6.4%, named IGT [2].

All the participants (prediabetes and control individuals) were informed to be overnight fast and in the morning to attend at laboratory department, clinical biochemistry unit of Azadi Teaching Hospital for blood collection. Five ml of blood was drawn from the study participants, 2 ml was collected immediately into a vacuum tube containing EDTA as an anticoagulant for estimation of HbA1c percent and 3 ml was collected in gel separator tubes. The serum was separated from the whole blood after clotting using a centrifugation process (HITACHI centrifuge, model O5P-21) at 5000 rpm for 10 min, and then the serum was processed for measuring serum glucose, insulin and afamin levels. The Cobas 6000 (Roche, Hitachi/ Germany) was used to analyze glucose, insulin and HbA1c depended upon enzyme colorimetric, electrochemiluminescence and turbidimetry methods. Serum afamin levels were assessed by Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA). Insulin resistance was indicated by Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) as follows: $\text{HOMA-IR} = \text{glucose (mg/dl)} \times \text{insulin } (\mu\text{u/l}) / 405$ [10].

Statistics

The general information among study groups (prediabetic individuals and healthy control participants) was shown as a mean (SD) or as a percentage. Independent t-tests and Pearson Chi-Square were utilized to compare the groups in the study. To compare the differences between the two groups, the Pearson Chi-square test was used. The correlations of serum afamin levels with biochemical measurements and characteristics of prediabetic participants were examined in bivariate regression

analysis. A p value of 0.05 or less is considered statistically significant. The statistical calculations were executed by the SPSS Program.

Results

The differences in general characteristics between prediabetic and healthy control participants were

found in Table 1. The mean age of prediabetic was (44.05±10.56) with males predominant (63.6%) and 70.5% were above 40 years of age. Moreover, the mean WC and BMI were significantly higher among prediabetic individuals (102.21±13.62 and 31.65±5.89).

Table 1: Comparison of General Information among Study Groups

Subject characteristics	Prediabetics n=44	Controls n=44	p value
	No %	No %	
Gender			
Male	28 (63.6%)	23 (52.3%)	0.194 ^a
Female	16 (36.4%)	21 (47.7%)	
Age (Mean± SD)	44.05±10.56	41.39±5.41	0.141 ^b
< 40 years	13 (29.5%)	21 (47.7%)	0.062 ^a
≥ 40 years	31 (70.5%)	23 (52.3%)	
WC (Mean± SD)	102.21±13.62	93.89±11.98	0.003^b
Male			
< 102 cm	15 (53.6%)	16 (69.6%)	0.191 ^a
≥ 102 cm	13 (46.4%)	7 (30.4%)	
Female			
< 88 cm	2 (12.5%)	11 (52.4%)	0.013^a
≥ 88 cm	14 (87.5%)	10 (47.6%)	
BMI (Mean± SD) (Kg/m²)	31.65±5.89	24.77±3.41	<0.001^b
Normal	5 (11.4%)	24 (54.5%)	<0.001^a
Overweight and obese	39 (88.6%)	20 (45.5%)	

^a Pearson Chi-Square and ^b independent T-test were performed for statistical analysis. The bold number is regarded as statistically significant.
WC: Waist Circumferences, BMI: Body Mass Index

The mean levels of serum glucose (105.54±5.89 mg/dl), whole blood HbA1C percent (6.04±0.23%), serum insulin (14.78±6.81ng/ml), and HOMA-IR (4.11±2.72) were significantly higher in prediabetic individuals compared to healthy control participants. As well as,

there were higher mean levels of serum afamin in prediabetic individuals (115.31±62.74) compared to their level in the control group (91.57±43.46 ng/ml), with a statistically significant difference (p = 0.042), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of Biochemical Measurements among Study Groups

Parameters	Prediabetics n=44	Controls n=44	p value
	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	
FPS mg/dl	105.54±5.89	79.9±8.2	<0.001
HbA1c %	6.04±0.23	5.08±0.30	<0.001
Insulin µIU/mL	14.78±6.81	12.12±4.13	0.029
HOMA-IR	4.11±2.72	2.45±0.87	<0.001
Afamin ng/ml	115.31±62.74	91.57±43.46	0.042

Independent T-test were performed for statistical analysis. The bold number is regarded as statistically significant.
FPS: fasting plasma glucose, HOMA-IR: homeostasis Modell assessment of Insulin Resistance

Table 3 showed there were insignificantly higher serum afamin levels with abnormally higher levels of biochemical parameters (HbA1C%, serum insulin

µIU/mL and HOMA-IR) in prediabetes individuals. The mean levels of serum afamin were higher in the males (> 40 years), and obese prediabetes individuals.

Table 3: Association of Serum Afamin with Different Levels of Biochemical Parameters and General Characteristics of Prediabetic Individuals

Parameters	Afamin in Prediabetics n=44		p value
	No%	Mean± SD	
FPG mg/dl < 99 ≥ 99	0 44 (100%)	115.31±62.74	NA
HbA1c % < 5.8 5.8 – 6.4%	38(86.4) 6(13.6%)	61.34±9.95 77.53±31.65	0.970
Insulin µIU/mL < 20 ≥ 20	7(15.9%) 37(84.1%)	95.45±15.49 119.07±67.61	0.376
HOMA-IR < 2.5 ≥ 2.5	9(20.5%) 35(79.5%)	113.39±80.61 115.81±58.73	0.919
Gender Male Female	28 (63.6%) 16 (36.4%)	124.43±72.77 99.35±36.43	0.206
Age < 40 years ≥ 40 years	13 (29.5%) 31 (70.5%)	108.37±65.16 118.22±62.57	0.640
WC Male < 102 cm ≥ 102 cm Female < 88 cm ≥ 88 cm	15 (53.6%) 13 (46.4%) 2 (12.5%) 14 (87.5%)	115.48±73.04 132.19±74.16 99.33±38.30 99.48±28.97	0.554 0.996
BMI (Kg/m²) Normal Overweight and obese	5 (11.4%) 39 (88.6%)	92.71±30.97 118.21±65.40	0.174
Independent T-tests were performed for statistical analysis. The bold number is regarded as statistically significant. WC: Waist Circumferences, BMI: Body Mass Index, FPS: fasting plasma glucose, HOMA-IR: homeostasis Modell assessment of Insulin Resistance			

The correlation of serum afamin level with the general characteristics and biochemical parameters of prediabetic participants is presented in Table 4. There was a statistically insignificant and positive correlation

between serum afamin and the general characteristics of prediabetic participants such as glucose, HbA1c, HOMA-IR, age, WC and BMI.

Table 4: Correlation of Serum Afamin Level with General Characteristics and Biochemical Parameters of Prediabetic Participants

Characters	Serum afamin in Prediabetics n=44	
	Pearson Correlation (r)	Sig. (2-tailed) (p value)
Age years	0.023	0.884
WC (cm)	0.063	0.686
BMI (Kg/m ²)	0.206	0.179
FPS (mg/dl)	0.012	0.940
HbA1c (%)	0.116	0.453
HOMA-IR	0.180	0.242
A statistical analysis was conducted using bivariate correlation. WC: Waist Circumferences, BMI: Body Mass Index, FPS: Fasting Plasma Glucose, HOMA-IR: Homeostasis Modell Assessment of Insulin Resistance		

Discussion

The present study showed that the frequency of prediabetes in obese (> 40 years) was higher than non-obese women (< 40 years). The results reveal that two-thirds of prediabetes individuals were men and this result was consistent with other study showed that men seem more susceptible than women to prediabetes, which is mostly related to differences in insulin sensitivity and regional fat deposition between both genders [11,12]. More than two-thirds of prediabetic individuals were more than 40 years old as the ageing process leads to decreased insulin secretion and increased insulin resistance predominantly in skeletal muscle [13].

In the current work, the majority of prediabetic individuals were overweight and obese compared to healthy control which was consistent with another study that observed a higher BMI and WC among prediabetic individuals. This relationship can be explained by the ageing process, physical inactivity (sedentary lifestyle) and accumulation of body fat causing chronic inflammation leading to dysfunction of β cells and insulin resistance [14,15]. Furthermore; physical activity increases the muscle's sensitivity to insulin, which facilitates the removal of blood glucose and controlling its blood levels [16]. Being inactive causes your muscles to become less sensitive to insulin, which makes it more difficult for the cells to utilize insulin as intended, this can ultimately lead to elevated blood glucose levels and prediabetes development [17,18].

The precise role of afamin in glucose metabolism is still unclear, but it's thought to be involved in fatty acid uptake and lipid metabolism in the liver [19,20]. The present data revealed significantly higher mean serum afamin levels in prediabetic individuals and it was positively correlated with increased HOMA-IR, and obesity (could trigger increased afamin production) compared to healthy control individuals. This was consistent with a prior study done by Kollerits and his colleagues in Germany, which showed higher mean serum afamin level in prediabetes and it was strongly associated with IR [21]. Prediabetes is characterized by continuous low-grade inflammation, as well as, afamin is considered an acute-phase protein, so this implies that afamin might serve as a marker for the inflammatory condition linked to prediabetes [22]. Physical activity that is associated with increased insulin sensitivity leads to a significant reduction in serum afamin levels suggesting that the plasma concentration of afamin is related to the individual anthropometric and metabolic risk factors such as obesity and increased HOMA-IR [23].

Additionally, the current study reveals a positive correlation of mean serum afamin with glycemic indices as other work observed a higher afamin level in

impaired glucose metabolism was frequently linked to glycemic indices (FSG, HbA1c%) and worse glycemic control, this may be brought on by the possibility of afamin involvement in the metabolism of glucose or by its interactions with other inflammatory processes that impact glycemic regulation [24]. Afamin may contribute to oxidative stress, another factor linked to insulin resistance and impaired glucose metabolism [25].

The limitation of the study was that we chose asymptomatic prediabetic individuals, and their diagnosis depends on laboratory investigations.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that the frequency of prediabetes in obese males, more than 40 years old, was higher than non-obese women less than 40 years. Moreover, the study reveals a significantly higher mean level of serum afamin among prediabetic individuals compared to the healthy control group, as well as, there was a positive correlation of serum afamin with obesity, HbA1c%, FPG and HOMA-IR.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Rett K, Gottwald-Hostalek U. Understanding prediabetes: definition, prevalence, burden and treatment options for an emerging disease. *Current Medical Research and Opinion*. 2019 Apr 15. Doi:10.1080/03007995.2019.1601455
- [2] American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee. American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee: Draznin B, Aroda VR, Bakris G, Benson G, Brown FM, Freeman R, et al. Facilitating Behavior Change and Well-being to Improve Health Outcomes: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2022. *Diabetes Care*. 2022;45(Suppl 1):S60-82. Doi: 10.2337/dc22-S005.
- [3] Abdullah BI, Salih SF. Lipoprotein (a) Level Among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and Prediabetes in Comparison with Healthy Controls. *Science Journal of University of Zakho*. 2023 Jan 1;11(1):30-6. Doi:10.25271/sjuoz.2023.11.1.996
- [4] Kronenberg F, Kollerits B, Kiechl S, et al. Plasma concentrations of afamin are associated with the prevalence and development of metabolic syndrome. *Circulation: cardiovascular genetics*. 2014 Dec;7(6):822-9. doi: 10.1161/CIRCGENETICS.113.000654.
- [5] Kaur R, Krishan P, Kumari P, et al. Clinical Significance of Adropin and Afamin in Evaluating Renal Function and Cardiovascular Health in the Presence of CKD-MBD Biomarkers in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Diagnostics*. 2023 Oct 9;13(19):3158. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13193158>
- [6] Kurdiová T, Balaz M, Kovaníková Z, et al. Serum afamin a novel marker of increased hepatic lipid content. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2021 Sep

16;12:670425.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2021.670425>

[7] Juhász I, Ujfalusi S, Seres I, et al. Afamin levels and their correlation with oxidative and lipid parameters in non-diabetic, obese patients. *Biomolecules*. 2022 Jan 12;12(1):116. doi: 10.3390/biom12010116

[8] Ahmed HH, Hameed ER, Shehata MA, et al. Relation between afamin level and some inflammatory markers in obese children. *Medical Research Journal*. 2015 Jun 1;14(1):1-6. DOI: 10.1097/01.MJX.0000464329.16129.c0

[9] Eroğlu Khanna D, Peltzer C, Kahar P, et al. Body mass index (BMI): a screening tool analysis. *Cureus*. 2022 Feb;14(2). doi: 10.7759/cureus.22119

[10] Jiménez-Maldonado A, García-Suárez PC, Rentería I, et al. Impact of high-intensity interval training and sprint interval training on peripheral markers of glycemic control in metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Molecular Basis of Disease*. 2020 Aug 1;1866(8):165820.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbadis.2020.165820>

[11] Andes LJ, Cheng YJ, Rolka DB, et al. Prevalence of prediabetes among adolescents and young adults in the United States, 2005-2016. *JAMA pediatrics*. 2020 Feb 1;174(2):e194498-. DOI: 10.1001/jamapediatrics.2019.4498

[12] Suleiman RR, Salih SF, Abdullah BI, et al. Triglyceride Glucose Index, its Modified Indices, and Triglyceride HDL-C Ratio as Predictor Markers of Insulin Resistance in Prediabetic Individuals. *Medical Journal of Babylon*. 2023 Apr 1;20(2):268-73. DOI:10.4103/MJBL.MJBL_269_22

[13] Arslanian SA, El Ghormli L, Kim JY, et al. OGTT glucose response curves, insulin sensitivity, and β -cell function in RISE: comparison between youth and adults at randomization and in response to interventions to preserve β -cell function. *Diabetes Care*. 2021 Mar 1;44(3):817-25. DOI: 10.2337/dc20-2134

[14] Ponti F, Santoro A, Mercatelli D, et al. Aging and imaging assessment of body composition: from fat to facts. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2020 Jan 14;10:861. DOI: 10.3389/fendo.2019.00861

[15] Zhang K, Ma Y, Luo Y, et al. Metabolic diseases and healthy aging: identifying environmental and behavioral risk factors and promoting public health. *Frontiers in Public Health*. 2023 Oct 13;11:1253506. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1253506>

[16] Navarro-Ledesma S, Hamed-Hamed D, González-Muñoz A, et al. Physical Activity, Insulin Resistance and Cancer: A Systematic Review. *Cancers*. 2024 Feb 3;16(3):656. doi: 10.3390/cancers16030656

[17] Hamburg NM, McMackin CJ, Huang AL, et al. Physical inactivity rapidly induces insulin resistance and microvascular dysfunction in healthy volunteers. *Arteriosclerosis, thrombosis, and vascular biology*. 2007 Dec 1;27(12):2650-6. DOI: 10.1161/ATVBAHA.107.153288

[18] Smith JA. Skeletal muscle responses to physical activity in health and metabolic disease. *Inst för fysiologi och farmakologi/Dept of Physiology and Pharmacology*; 2024 Jan 12. <http://hdl.handle.net/10616/48948>

[19] Kurdiova T, Balaz M, Kovanicova Z, et al. Serum afamin a novel marker of increased hepatic lipid content. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2021 Sep 16;12:670425.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2021.670425>

[20] Eroğlu H, Örgül G, Tonyalı NV, et al. The role of afamin and other trace elements in the prediction of GDM: a tertiary center experience. *Biological Trace Element Research*. 2021 Dec;199:4418-22. DOI: 10.1007/s12011-020-02559-0

[21] Kollerits B, Lamina C, Huth C, et al. Plasma concentrations of afamin are associated with prevalent and incident type 2 diabetes: a pooled analysis in more than 20,000 individuals. *Diabetes care*. 2017 Oct 1;40(10):1386-93. DOI: 10.2337/dc17-0201

[22] Chen W, Xiong B, Liao Z, et al. Association between dietary inflammatory index and low muscle mass in diabetes/prediabetes patients. *Experimental Gerontology*. 2023 Aug 1;179:112258. DOI: 10.1016/j.exger.2023.112258

[23] Maiorca C, Acitelli E, Grani G, et al. Metabolic adverse events of multitarget kinase inhibitors: A systematic review. *Atherosclerosis*. 2023 Aug 1;379:S104-5. doi: 10.1007/s12020-023-03362-2

[24] Nowicki GJ, Ślusarska B, Polak M, et al. Relationship between serum kallistatin and afamin and anthropometric factors associated with obesity and of being overweight in patients after myocardial infarction and without myocardial infarction. *Journal of clinical medicine*. 2021 Dec 10;10(24):5792. DOI: 10.3390/jcm10245792

[25] Köninger A, Mathan A, Mach P, et al. Is Afamin a novel biomarker for gestational diabetes mellitus? A pilot study. *Reproductive Biology and Endocrinology*. 2018 Dec;16:1-1. DOI: 10.1186/s12958-018-0338-x

